

PREVALENCE OF THYROID CANCER

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Annotation. The prevalence of nodular lesions of the thyroid gland (thyroid gland), according to various researchers, ranges from 3 to 7%. The widespread introduction of ultrasound into clinical practice, as well as the results of autopsy studies, have shown that the prevalence of nodular lesions of the thyroid gland is much higher and is about 50%, especially at the age of over 50 years. In women, thyroid nodes are detected 2-4 times more often than in men.

Keywords: thyroid cancer, occurrence, clinic, diagnosis.

Children suffer from nodular lesions extremely rarely. The incidence of nodular goiter is directly proportional to age. The increase in the incidence of nodular goiter is approximately 0.1% per year at a young age and gradually reaches 2%. The prevalence of thyroid cancer among nodular goiter, according to various authors, ranges from 1 to 6%. It should be noted that the prevalence in the population of nodular goiter is so high both in regions of iodine deficiency and with normal iodine supply, but in the first case it is slightly higher. The incidence of breast cancer in absolute numbers does not depend on the level of iodine provision. Thus, in a situation of a slightly higher incidence of banal nodular colloidal goiter in the regions of one deficit, the proportion of cancer among all cases of nodular goiter will be less here. It is important to note that these data make it possible to equally use the results of studies on breast cancer obtained in regions with different iodine supply. The prevalence of nodular lesions of the thyroid gland (thyroid gland), according to various researchers, ranges from 3 to 7% [1]. The widespread introduction of ultrasound into clinical practice, as well as the results of autopsy studies, have shown that the prevalence of nodular lesions of the thyroid gland is significantly higher and is about 50%, especially at the age of over 50 years [10]. In women, thyroid nodes are detected 2-4 times more often than in men. Children suffer from nodular lesions extremely rarely. The incidence of nodular goiter is directly proportional to age. The increase in the incidence of nodular goiter is approximately 0.1% per year at a young age and gradually reaches 2% [97, 108]. The prevalence of thyroid cancer among nodular goiter, according to various authors, ranges from 1 to 6% [1, 8]. It should be noted that the prevalence in the population of nodular goiter is so high both in regions of iodine deficiency and with normal iodine supply, but in the first case it is slightly higher. The incidence of prostate cancer in absolute numbers does not depend on the level of iodine supply [1, 7]. Thus, in a situation of a slightly higher incidence of banal nodular colloidal goiter in regions of iodine deficiency, the proportion of cancer among all cases of nodular goiter will be less here. It is important to note that these data make it possible to equally use the results of studies on breast cancer obtained in regions with different iodine supply. Clinically diagnosed prostate cancer accounts for less than 1% of all human malignant tumors. Morphological examination of the removed thyroid tissue showed that the prevalence of occult prostate cancer reaches 10%. At the same time, breast cancer is the cause of death from all oncological diseases only in 0.3—0.5% of cases [4, 5]. The annual detection of prostate cancer varies in different countries from 0.5 to 10 per 100,000 population [2, 4, 9]. Prostate cancer is as common as myeloma, cancer of the esophagus, larynx, mouth, cervix. Prostate cancer is the most common endocrine malignant disease (about 90% of all endocrine

malignant tumors). According to the American Cancer Society, about 17,000 new cases of the disease and about 1,300 deaths associated with prostate cancer are registered in the United States each year. However, due to adequate treatment, survival in breast cancer is quite high. In the USA, approximately 190 thousand patients with prostate cancer have survived more than 40 years after diagnosis [4, 3,9]

Prostate cancer can develop from both follicular (A- and B-cells) and parafollicular cells (C-cells). There are 4 morphological forms of prostate cancer from follicular cells: papillary cancer (including the follicular variant), follicular cancer, cancer from Güttele-Ashkenazi cells (oxyfilnocellular) and anaplastic cancer. From parafollicular cells, medullary PCR occurs [8, 5]. According to the US National Cancer Database (NCDB), out of 53,856 patients who received treatment for prostate cancer from 1985 to 1995, 80% had papillary adenocarcinoma, 11% — follicular adenocarcinoma, 3% — adenocarcinoma from Güttele—Ashkenazi cells, 4% — medullary adenocarcinoma and 2% — anaplastic adenocarcinoma [5]. The death rate from PCR in the USA in 2001 (according to NCDB) was about 1,300 deaths per 135,000 patients (about 1%) [4].

Despite the fact that women suffer from breast cancer more often, mortality is higher among men. Apparently, this is due to the fact that men who have been diagnosed with prostate cancer belong to an older age group than women [6, 11]. Each morphological variant of breast cancer has its own characteristic features of development, which significantly affects the prognosis [5, 7, 1].

Over the past 20 years, there has been an increase in the incidence of prostate cancer by almost 28%, while reducing mortality by more than 23%. The causes of this phenomenon are statistically insufficiently studied. This is most likely due to the fact that the widespread introduction of ultrasound and puncture biopsy of the thyroid gland into clinical practice has led to a much more effective detection of the early stages of the disease, in which the prognosis of surgical treatment in combination with radioactive iodine therapy is most favorable [7].

Controversial issues of diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer

Despite the unanimous recognition of fine needle puncture biopsy (TPB) as the "gold standard" in the diagnosis of thyroid tumors, the details of therapeutic tactics remain a subject of discussion among researchers. Currently, there is no consensus [1] on the following issues:

Choosing the optimal volume of surgery for prostate cancer — thyroidectomy or organ-preserving operations.

Indications for intervention on the lymph nodes of the neck.

The role of postoperative therapy with radioactive iodine.

Principles of long-term suppressive therapy.

The protocol of observation of the patient (the set and frequency of control studies, the duration of the dispensary registration). Unfortunately, the number of long-term prospective randomized trials evaluating the long-term results of treatment of patients receiving various options for prostate cancer therapy is very limited. Therefore, in order to solve these controversial issues of diagnosis and treatment of prostate cancer, it is necessary to analyze these few studies and materials from some national databases on prostate cancer.

To predict the results of treatment of patients with prostate cancer, it is necessary to analyze certain factors on the basis of which one or another therapeutic tactic is chosen and the subsequent observation of patients. Despite the optimistic survival rates, the likelihood of relapse of the disease has existed for many decades. Monitoring of patients and the study of long-term results of treatment of prostate cancer is necessary in terms of 10 to 30 years or more, which is dictated by a sufficiently long development of the disease. Adequate monitoring should be carried out using modern medical capabilities and involving various specialists — endocrinologists, surgeons, oncologists, radiologists [1].

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